

Principles of Editing and Storytelling in Relation to Editorial Graphic Design

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Abstract : This paper aims to combine film editing principles to basic design principles to explore what graphic designers do in terms of storytelling. The sequential aspect of film is designed and examined through the art of editing. Examining the rules, principles and formulas of film editing can be a method for graphic designers to further practice the art of storytelling. Although there are many research and publications on design basics, time, pace, dramatic structure and choreography are not very well defined in the area of graphic design. In this era of creative storytelling and interdisciplinary collaboration, not only film editors but also graphic designers and students in the arts and design should understand the theory and practice of editing to be able to create a strong mise-en-scène and not only a mise-en-page.

Keywords : design principles, editing principles, editorial design, film editing, graphic design, storytelling

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